

Importance of *Ayurvedic Nidanam Pariksha's* to Improve the Accuracy of Diagnosis in General Clinical Practice

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Abstract— In day today's general clinical practice proper diagnosis of the disease plays an important role considering the further treatment point of view for that particular disorder.

Proper history taking along with sound physical examination can improve the accuracy of the final diagnosis of the disease. If history is not taken in proper way, it will affect the entire diagnosis process which ultimately resulted in wrong implementation of treatment which can affect general health of the patient adversely.

In Ayurvedic classical literatures our ancient Acharya have described importance of proper history taking along with *Rugnapariksha*.

षडविधो हि रोगाणां विज्ञानोपायः।

तद्यथा पञ्चभिः श्रोत्रादिभिः प्रश्नेन चेति ॥

सु.सू. १०/०४

As described in above reference of *Sushruta Samhita*, proper history taking i.e. *Prashna* along with physical examination with *Panchdnyanendriya* is very important for accurate *Nidanam* of the disease. It can also reduce the margins of errors which can ultimately very useful to improve generalized health of the patient by getting accurate treatment of that particular disorder.

त्रिविधं खलु रोगविशेष विज्ञानं भवति।

तद्यथा आप्तोपदेशः प्रत्यक्षं अनुमानं चेति ॥

च.वि. ०४/०३

In above reference Acharya Charaka have described the importance of the *Trividha Pariksha*. *Aptopadesh* means previous studies and experiments. *Pratyaksham* means sound physical examination and *Anumanam* means to make provisional diagnosis according to the physical examination and previous studies. These *Trividha Karmas* are very important in diagnosis process of any disease.

The main limitation of today's general practice is, modern science diagnosis is mainly depend upon pathological & radiological investigations. But in remote or rural areas due to lack of investigation modalities general practitioners faces lots of difficulties during practice. So here with the implementation of *Trividha* & *Shadvidha Pariksha* we can make the accurate diagnosis and accordingly utilize proper line of treatment of that particular disorder of the patient. That is why *Ayurvedic Nidanam Pariksha* are the need of today's general practice.

Keywords— *Rugnapariksha*, Diagnosis, *Panchdnyanendriya*, *Nidanam*, *Trividha Pariksha*, History Taking, *Aptopadesh*, *Pratyaksham*, *Anumanam*, *Shadavidha Pariksha*.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ayurvedic *Nidan Pariksha's* are the need of today's general practice. As most of the diagnostic views in modern general practice are depend upon pathological investigations and radiological findings of the patient. It is not possible to do these investigations everywhere especially in rural and remote areas. We have to diagnose patient according his/her recent physical examination as well as proper history taking which provided by patient and his /

her relatives or lay man who brought him towards you. Here *Ayurvedic Nidan Pariksha's* plays very important role to do the accurate diagnosis and accordingly we can utilize the appropriate line of treatment for better outcome.

So here we are going to discuss about all these *Ayurvedic Nidan Pariksha's* and how they can help for making accurate diagnosis. Also we are going to study about various references described in *Ayurvedic* classical literatures regarding *Nidan Pariksha's* and also their importance in today's general practice to make accurate diagnosis of the particular disorder

which can help physicians to utilize accurate treatment for that particular disorder. This is very important to achieve good outcomes of the treatment. This is very important as it provides very good relief to the patients from complaints of that particular disease and also helps to boost up the confidence of the physician during general practice.

II. AIM AND OBJECTIVE

Here we are going to study the importance and efficiency of *Ayurvedic Nidan Pariksha's* to improve the accuracy of diagnosis in general clinical practice

In our various classical literatures of *Ayurveda*, our ancient *Acharya* have specifically mentioned the importance of *Nidan Pariksha's* during general check up of the patient in various *Ayurvedic Samhita Granthas*. So we have to elaborate these important terms which are described in our ancient *Samhita Granthas* and have to study that how they can help the physicians to utilize proper line of treatment for particular disorder accordingly.

And also if someone ignore these *Nidan Pariksha's* during general health check up of the patient, it can result into serious consequences regarding patient's health and also physician can't utilize proper treatment to cure the health related problem of that patient. Also such physician always remains dependent on pathological and radiological findings for making diagnosis.

So here we are going to study how proper utilization of *Ayurvedic Nidanam Pariksha's* are very important for physicians in day today's general clinical practice.

III. OBSERVATION

Pramana Pariksha's Importance:-

Pratyaksha Pramana-

Pratyaksha is the best method of knowledge because it is obtained from direct contact of sense organs. So here physician can directly observe the patient with his sense organ i.e. *Panchdnyanendriya* and accordingly can think about the abnormalities he found during patient examination.

Anuman Pramana-

Here physician have to take the help of logical inferences. For example in follow up study of arthritis patients measuring the joint swelling by measuring tape is *Pratyaksha Pariksha* but when physician want to access overall improvement, he can ask patient to walk for a distance. Here if patient is walking without support and without pain after some course of medicine then physician can logically make interpretation that treatment is acting well.

Aptopadesha Pramana-

Aptopadesha Pramana is the base of all *Pramana*. All the successful practitioners have mentioned their case study reports regarding particular diseases in various books or journals. Also they share their experiences regarding specific complicated cases they face during their practice or research. So physician have to read & gain knowledge from all these documentation to improve and elaborate his/her knowledge. This is very important for practicing more confidently and successfully by gaining the knowledge from previous experiences of experts.

Shadavidha Nidan Pariksha's-

This is very important section to make proper diagnosis during general check up of the patient. Proper history taking i.e. *Prashna* along with physical examination with *Panchdnyanendriya* is very important for accurate *Nidanam* of the disease. Here examination of patients with 5 senses and 6th is proper history taking i.e. *Prashna* are combinely mentioned as *Shadavidha Pariksha*.

Here in *Prashna* i.e. history taking we carefully have to collect all detailed information regarding health issues of the patient. We have to get accurate information regarding duration of that particular disorder so that we can get idea whether that disorder is acute or chronic. We also have to ask history of comorbid disorder if patient have any. Also we have to collect information about history of major illness or surgery if patient had suffer previously and also allergic reactions of any drug or any other thing which patient is suffering if any.

In day today medical practice to evaluate *Swastha* or healthy person following reference from *Kashyap Samhita* is more practical-

समदोषः समाग्निश्च समधातुमलक्रियः।

प्रसन्नात्मेन्द्रियमनः स्वस्थ इत्याभिधियते ॥

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By this reference doctor can easily ask following 4 questions and can make provisional diagnosis of healthy or unhealthy conditions.

- How is appetite or hunger?
- How is condition of stool or urine?
- Whether there is sound sleep and patient feel energetic after night sleep?
- Whether person can maintain his normal activities like sensory & motor functions?

According to answers of these questions comparing standard protocol of healthy individuals physician can make provisional diagnosis of healthy or unhealthy conditions.

In physical examination of the patient with eyes we have to observe the body & skin texture of the patient. We have to observe whether that patient is thick or thin. Also we have to check patient's appearance. With ear we have to check his/her heart sounds, Intestinal sounds, character of voice of patient, cracking sound in joint. With Nose we can sense the abnormalities or foul smelling of injuries or wounds, with tongue not directly but by logical inferences we can check the diabetic foot patients by presence of maggots in wound. And lastly by touch we can sense the abnormalities of body temperature of patient or also tendered site of body site which is suggestive of tissue injury at that particular site. Also in supported wound or in abscesses we can feel fluctuation at wound site.

IV. RESULT

Here considering the treatment without all these mentioned *Nidan Pariksha's*, physician can't do proper diagnosis of the patient and always depend on pathological and radiological findings for making diagnosis of the disease which is not

affordable for poor patients and also not available at remote ruler places.

Also with proper examination of the patient as mentioned in *Ayurvedic Nidan Pariksha's*, with the help of the sense organs, physician can make his/her provisional diagnosis according to the *Nidan Pariksha's* and can utilize accurate line of treatment for that particular disorder.

Also in *Prashna*, by proper and detailed history taking physician can decide whether patient need any urgent further radiological investigation or any surgical intervention or not. As in blunt trauma where there is very little external injuries but internal haemorrhage must have to rule out and treat urgently to save the life and avoid further complications to the patient.

In such cases of head injuries or severe blunt trauma due to road traffic accidents also by proper *Darshan Pariksha* physician can check whether the patient is well conscious and oriented or semiconscious and disoriented or totally unconscious. This is very important for deciding further line of treatment of the patient.

V. CONCLUSION

The main limitation of today's general practice is, modern science diagnosis is mainly depend upon pathological & radiological investigations. But in remote or rural areas due to lack of investigation modalities general practitioners faces lots of difficulties during practice. So here with the implementation of *Trividha & Shadvidha Pariksha* we can make the accurate diagnosis and accordingly utilize proper line of treatment of that particular disorder of the patient. That is why *Ayurvedic Nidanam Pariksha* are the need of today's general practice.

Also if someone ignore these *Nidan Pariksha's* during general health check up of the patient, it can resulted into serious consequences regarding patient's health and also physician can't utilize proper treatment to cure the health related problem of that patient. Also such physician always remains dependent on pathological and radiological findings for making diagnosis.

In our various classical literatures of *Ayurveda*, our ancient *Acharya* have specifically mentioned the importance of *Nidan Pariksha's* during general check up of the patient in various *Ayurvedic Samhita Granthas*. So we have to elaborate these important terms which are described in our ancient *Samhita Granthas* and have to study that how they can help the physicians to utilize proper line of treatment for particular disorder accordingly.

From all above mentioned points we can conclude that *Ayurvedic Nidan Pariksha's* are very important tools during patient examination and very useful and important also for improving accuracy of the diagnosis and accordingly for starting appropriate line of treatment.

In today's modern era also if physician utilize modern diagnostic techniques like pathological and radiological investigations after detail and appropriate *Ayurvedic Nidan Pariksha's* it will become very helpful to treat the disorder and physician can achieve a great success and it will also help him/her to practice more confidently.

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